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**THE PRAGMATIC ASPECT OF VERBALIZATION OF
THE CONCEPT REFUGEE IN THE BRITISH MASS
MEDIA**

Oleksandr YEMETS

(Khmelnyskyi National University, Ukraine)

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6332-2830>

Oleksandr Yemets. The Pragmatic aspect of Verbalization of the Concept of Refugee in the British mass media. The paper deals with the language means of verbalization of the concept REFUGEE. The research is based on “The Guardian” and “BBC News” articles. The stages of analyzing the pragmatic aspect of the concept are suggested. The first stage consists of defining the etymology of the core word. The second stage involves selecting and analyzing the lexical units verbalizing the concept. The third stage is aimed at characterizing the pragmatic aspect of verbalization. Our research revealed that the core lexical units include such words as refugee, to flee, asylum seeker, care, and support. The analysis of the pragmatic aspect contained two points: the description of the Ukrainian refugees, their psychological state, and their problems in the British mass media; the feedback from the Ukrainian asylum-seekers, mainly women and children, concerning the attitude toward them from the host families, at school, and in everyday situations. The British media portrayal of the Ukrainian refugees is positive, the cultural similarities and the educational level of the Ukrainians are emphasized. The feedback from the refugees includes words with positive connotations: generous, heartwarming, exceptional, and politeness.

Keywords: *refugee, concept, conceptual analysis, stage of analysis, core units, verbalization, pragmatic aspect, feedback.*

The aggression of Russia against Ukraine caused not only military and political problems but also resulted in the linguistic analysis of the existing and new military

terminology and the investigation of lexical and pragmatic aspects of the political speeches of our President and other world leaders. To understand and rethink the situation and the fate of our country and our people, we may use the principles of conceptual analysis.

Concepts can be defined as mental structures used by a person in the process of thinking and communication (Sukhorolska, 2006, p. 245). Concepts are expressed by words, i.e. verbalized. Verbalization takes place at different levels - in the official atmosphere and in everyday life, in different types of discourse – written or oral. The most common lexical concepts involve social notions (PEACE, WAR, FRIENDSHIP), moral concepts (TRUTH, LIE), scientific concepts, etc. One of the social concepts that attracts much attention is refugees. It is caused by the arrival of millions of Ukrainians as refugees in many European countries. This concept is associated with other concepts like SYMPATHY, CARE, and SAFETY. How the concept REFUGEE is reflected in different media has become the object of research for Ukrainian scientists. Thus, A. V. Milyo investigates the reflection of this concept in the German mass media and social networks (2020). A. Matveyeva considers the lexical aspect of the concept REFUGEE / БІЖЕНЕЦЬ in the Ukrainian legal discourse. It is interesting to note that quite recently, two scientists from Indonesia performed a discursive analysis concerning the fact of how four leading British newspapers describe the state of the Ukrainian refugees. The discursive methods used are humanization and individualization. They also stressed that while Ukrainian refugees are characterized mostly positively, the refugees from non-European countries are portrayed negatively (Muhandar, Akmal, 2023, pp. 1583-1584). However, the conceptual analysis of the concept REFUGEE and the pragmatic aspect of its verbalization in the British mass media has not yet been performed.

The purpose of this paper consists in determining the lexical means of verbalization of the concept REFUGEE and the pragmatic effect of its verbalization, in particular in connection with the microconcepts CARE and SYMPATHY.

The first stage of the conceptual analysis includes defining the core unit – refugee – of the concept. The Oxford Advanced Learner's Dictionary states that it denotes a person

who is forced to leave his/her country and to seek shelter (protection) from political or religious persecution (OALD, 1989, p. 1058). According to Amnesty International, “a refugee is a person who has fled their own country because they are at risk of serious human rights violations and persecution”.

We have analyzed 20 short articles from “The Guardian” and “BBC News”. The second stage of our research involved determining the lexical units of verbalization of the concept. The core lexical units include such words and word combinations: *refugee, asylum-seeker, to flee, support, tolerance, etc.* One of the aspects often described is the adaptation of the Ukrainian refugees to the British way of life: *When Svetlana Chelisheva and her two daughters fled to the UK from Chernihiv, there were several strands of British life to adapt to as refugees* (“The Guardian”). The articles devoted to the psychological state of the Ukrainian refugees and the attitude of the British population have words with positive evaluative connotations and include such lexical units as *supportive, heartwarming, politeness of the British people; they were always hugged.*

So, we can consider two points in how the concept is verbalized in the British mass media. First of all, how the British mass media and the British people perceive the Ukrainians who arrived in the country, i.e., the attitude toward our refugees. The second point in the pragmatic aspect includes the feedback of the Ukrainians. According to the British Psychological Society, media portrayal of Ukrainian refugees was unusually positive: *There was emphasis placed on the cultural similarities of Ukrainian refugees with their country of refuge* (“BBC News”). Our refugees are educated, tolerant and have, in most cases, of European mentality. Both the British government and ordinary people displayed sympathy and support for the refugees; they helped the Ukrainians in many ways, mostly by giving them accommodation. Barry Lewis expressed the opinion of many Britons: *We as a country can be proud of our achievements in taking in close to 90, 000 refugees since last March. The household response has been phenomenal, particularly in England's county and rural areas* (“The Guardian”). Therefore, among the core words verbalizing the concept as seen by the British people, we can see the words enthusiasm, generosity, and *integrating these guests.*

The feedback from the Ukrainian asylum-seekers is especially positive. In the recent article in “The Guardian” (February 23, 2025), V. Klimova, 72, says: “*I have been so well received. The UK is a very good country for refugees*”.

In return she treats the English people with her homemade borsch, saying that sharing food is a good way to know the people. Another woman, Svitlana Tselisheva, appreciates how her daughters were received at school: “*They were always hugged, were always cared for*”. One of the key core units reflecting the attitude of the British people to the Ukrainians, mainly women, and children, is the noun *tolerance*, used 12 times in this article.

Conclusions. The pragmatic aspects of verbalization of the concept REFUGEE in the two mentioned British media contain lexical units with positive evaluative meanings. Such characteristic features of the Ukrainian refugees are emphasized as high cultural and educational levels. The feedback from the Ukrainians includes stressing such features of the British people as generosity, politeness, care and sympathy. It is necessary to note the emotional character of such publications.

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